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Thessaloniki, 26/5/2026

Attn.
Maria Katsikari
Project Manager- DigiMedFor

**Thirteenth International Conference on Environmental Management,
Engineering, Planning and Economics (CEMEPE 2026) & SECOTOX
Conference**

Dear Ms. Katsikari,

We are pleased to inform you that your paper entitled "**Autonomous Multi-modal Drone Scanning for High-Precision Forest Inventory: A Real-World Experiment in Limnia Forest Using Advanced YOLO Pipelines and Local Allometrics**" has been accepted for oral presentation at the at the Thirteenth International Conference on Environmental Management, Engineering, Planning and Economics (CEMEPE 2026) and SECOTOX Conference that will be held in Thessaloniki, Greece, from July 12 to 16, 2026. The event will be well attended, and your participation will enhance the aims of the Conference.

Looking forward to welcoming you in Thessaloniki, Greece.

Yours sincerely

Athanasios Kungolos
CEMEPE 2026 Organizing Committee Chairman